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THE CONCEPT OF STRESS AND ITS MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES

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Abstract

With the evolution of civilization and advancement of technology, life has become more unpredictable and prone to stress. The current economic crisis is one of the biggest causes of worry for people, even in the most advanced countries. The World Health Organization predicts that stress will be the number one killer in the world by the year 2020. Through the proper understanding of the concept of energy, working of mind, will power and energy management and its practice in sophisticated way we can make a stress free life as the byproduct.

Introduction

Stress in varying degrees has become a part of everyone's life due to a shift from traditional to modern lifestyle. Stress may be best defined as a psycho-physiological process, usually experienced as a negative emotional state, resulting from physical or psychosocial demands (Agarwal and Marshall, 2001 [1]). Stress can be categorized in several ways (Larzelere and Jones, 2008 [13]): Duration (acute/chronic), domain (physical/psychological), and severity (traumatic/daily hassles). Stress produces both adaptive and maladaptive effects on the physiological system. The burden of chronic stress can cause inhibition of neurogenesis, disruption of neuronal plasticity, even neurotoxicity (McEwen, 2007 [15]). Further, accompanying changes in personal behaviour due to chronic stress cause wear and tear in the body ("allostatic load"), which in turn alters physical and mental health (Juster et al., 2010 [8]).

Analyzing Stress

Mind is the fountainhead of desires and emotions. It seems it cannot survive without them. Desires appear in the mind incessantly, like the waves in an ocean. Even while dreaming, we have desires. When a desire is fulfilled, we feel a sense of satisfaction, albeit, temporary. Soon we start dreaming again—this time for yet another desire.

Stress can begin when we foresee a sense of failure. An uneasy feeling develops in the mind. Feelings of dread and apprehension about the future, with or without any specific cause, disturb our mind. It becomes stressed, because it perceives some strong obstacles in the achievement of its goals. Although stress originates in the mind, it spreads its influence all over the body. Clinical studies have shown that stress is the root cause of more diseases than was previously thought.

Model of stress response according to classical Yoga texts

The Classical Yoga texts model of stress is explained as imbalance in different kośas. In waking state, occurrence of an event or demanding situation results in repeated thinking and further leads to attachment (saṅgah). Intense attachment (kāma) in its turn, leads to an avalanche of thoughts (strong likes and dislikes). When this avalanche of thoughts is unfulfilled, it transforms into intense anger (krodhah):

Dhyāyato viṣayān pūmsaḥ saṅgasteṣupajāyate Śaṅgāt sañjāyate kāmaḥ
kāmaṅkrodho'bhijāyate \

Bhagavad Gita\2\62\ [When a man thinks of the objects, attachment for them arises; from attachment desire is born; from desire anger arises (Sivananda, 2013 [25])]

Intense Kāma and Krodha set out an involuntary impulse in the vijñānanmayakośa:

śaknotīhaiva yaḥ soḍhum prākṣarīravimokṣanāt \

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Kāmakrodhodbhavaṁ vegam sa yuktaḥ sa sukḥi naraḥ \\
 Bhagavad Gīta \5\23\ [He who is able, while still here (in this world) to withstand, before

the liberation from the body, the impulse born out of desire and anger - he is a Yogi, he is a happy man (Sivananda, 2013 [25]).

For a person who is able to withstand the impulses born out of desire and anger, all the actions will be governed by total knowledge based at the vijñānamaya kośa. Hence there will not be any adhi (stress) and the person achieves a state of perfect mental health. Those who do not have mastery over involuntary impulses due to desire and anger, continue towards infatuation, lack of awareness, and power of discrimination at vijñānamaya kośa:

Krodhātbhavati sammohaḥ sammohāt smṛtīvibhramaḥ Smṛtibhramśāt buddhināśo
 buddhināśāt praśāsyati \\
 Bhagavad Gīta \2\63\ [From anger comes delusion; from delusion loss of memory; from

loss of memory the destruction of discrimination; from the destruction of discrimination he perishes (Sivananda, 2013 [25])]

Further, vijñānamaya kośa endows manomaya kośa with unending thought processes and wrong cognition which leads to and manifests as adhi (stress) (Nagendra and Nagarathna, 2003 [18]). When the manomaya kośa is afflicted, the body follows the disturbance completely. Due to these disturbances, flow of prāṇa in nadis gets vitiated. These imbalances in the flow of prāṇa at the prāṇamayā kośa finally culminate in disease at the annamayā kośa or physical body level.

Citte vidhurite dehaḥ saṅkṣobham upayāti hi Saṅkṣobhāt sāmyam utsṛjya vahanti
 prāṇavāyavaḥ \\
 Yogavāsiṣṭha \25\3.35\ [When the mind is agitated, the body indeed goes to the state of

agitation. On account of agitation, the vital airs (or currents of bioenergy) flow, giving up evenness. (Jñānānanda, 1982 [26])]

Stress management

Energy

Life is the manifestations where you direct your energy truly is and what we really start with actually look at energy the same way we look at water. If we took water in a can and water to garden bed, are the leafs grow or flowers grow? both right where the water has no ability to discriminate the leaf and flowers, whatever things are start grow. Energy is someway well, if took energy and invested in something in negative and it become more negative and if we took energy and invested in positive and it become more positive as well. Energy has no ability to discriminate what's negative and what positive. Whatever energy invests into start grows and manifest in your life.

Right now you are the same total of where you have been investing the energy through your enter life. So the goal really in life is to figure out what it is you want? What is your purpose of your life? Who and what's important in your life and be able to direct energy towards the things so you can manifest that in your life.

How the monkey mind works?

So where do we begin with this, we began with understanding how the mind works. To understand the works of mind we have to understand two things, one is the awareness and another is the mind. Lets define what they are, the awareness is a glowing ball of light so imagine of a glowing ball of light the can float around let's call it awareness and put that aside.

Now let's define the mind with vast space with many different area within it, one area of the mind is angry, hatred, jealousy, joy happiness, sex, food, arts, science, technology etc. whole bunch of different things

Our awareness, that ball of glowing light can actually move any area of the mind you want it to go to. So, the awareness the glowing ball of light goes to the happy area of the mind then its lights up the particular area of the mind, you become conscious being happy, so are you

happy? No you are in area of mind called happiness. If this ball light goes to the energy area of the mind, it lights up the particular area of the mind, so are you angry? No, you are in area of mind called anger.

Will power

By using your will power and power of your concentration you can actually take your awareness, this ball of light to any area of the mind you want to go to. And here is the most important part where your awareness goes that's where your energy is flowing. So your energy flows into the angry area of the mind, your energy is flowing that and strengthening that particular area of mind. So this is the theory of it.

So really the goal in life is not really control your mind rather than control where your awareness is going within your mind. So don't control your mind, control where your awareness goes within your mind.

Concentration

How do we do that? We learn fine art of concentration. So at first let's define the concentration, the concentration is the ability to keep your awareness on one thing for an extended period of time. Sometimes we getting distracted but we have to return on that particular things, being able to do this that allows us to concentrate.

Most of the people can't concentrate for two reason, one is they never been taught how to concentrate and second is the never practice concentration. If you want to good at something you have to practice it, if you really get good concentration you need to practice concentration all day. People are good at destruction because that's what they practice all day along. It's not the day they don't have the ability to concentrate, they have just practice destructions and become really really good at it.

How to concentrate

So how do we concentrate, we concentrate by practicing by doing one thing at a time and integrating this practice into everyday of our life. We need to find out what's reoccurring event in our life, there have to give undivided attention, it drifts away but have to bring it back have to keep our awareness on that and have to give our undivided attention. By the end of the day we practicing awareness eight or ten hours of our life and three months letter we really good at concentration.

Will power

The other things we learn to develop our will power. Everybody is born various levels of will power but one thing we never get taught to do is how actually develop the will power and will power is like a muscle, we can call it mental biceps, we can grow it.

The three ways to develop the will power

1. Finish that what you begin
2. Finish it well, beyond your expectation
3. Do little bit more then you think that you are able to do.

All this three ways required effort and that effort is will power. Take these three methods and apply what the reoccurring in our life like every day we sleep then do it well managed before going to the bed, away from the destruction and sleep well and get up in the morning and finish it well with making the bed with great gratitude.

Energy management and its investment

Next thing we learn to do how the energy can manage in our life, we have finite amount of energy each day. Take our energy and investing in people or things around us we keep investing, investing, investing until no more energy is left. We get exhausted and we go to sleep and our energy builds up again. One thing most people do is we never evaluate who and what investing our energy in so we should treat energy as we treat money. It's the finite resource to be

wisely manage, wisely reallocated and wisely invested. No matter how rich you are you only have so much money and before spent money more of us think and evaluate where we are investing our money in. The great impetus of managing energy is death by which we can realize the life is finite that we only have one life. We should extremely clear where to focus our energy, there is no point to learning concentrates if we don't know what to concentrate on.

Energy vampires

People and things are the two biggest consumers of energy, people and things also give a lot of energy. Let's focus on people that consume energy and how we can deal with them. This person can be called as an energy vampire. To get rid of them one is we should fractionally detached is not engage to someone, surly to be kind, to be gentle, to be sincere and loving towards them but not engaging with them. Other way to protect self from an energy vampire is to place of responsibility on them means if you are somebody develop particular skill or you have expert in particular knish or particular area and you find that people want your time, they want your energy the one simple way to protect yourself is to place burden of responsibility on them. Give them a simple task to do and see if they do it and if they complete the task and come back to you then go for help them.

So it is clear to say that if we can understand the concept energy, working of mind, will power and energy management and practice in proper way to make good at it, then we can drown a stress free life as the byproduct.

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